

Studies on the Citrate Complexes of Zinc(II) and Manganese(II)

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The citrate complex of zinc and manganese have been studied by pH titration method and the results corroborated by the measurements of sp. conductances. The reactions taking place may be represented by

The equilibrium constants of the reactions (1), (2), (3), and (4) are respectively 6.36×10^{-3} , 4.89×10^{-3} , 2.00×10^{-8} , and 1.35×10^{-3} for zinc citrate and 1.33×10^{-3} , 1.95×10^{-3} , 3.07×10^{-9} , and 2.97×10^{-7} for manganese citrate.

Shin Suzuki (*J. Chem., Soc., Japan, Pure Chem. Sect.*, 1951, 72, 974) determined the equilibrium constant of zinc citrate complex by potentiometric method with the following ion cell and hydrogen electrode: Hg, HgCl, KCl, KCl, citric acid, ZnSO₄, H₂, and found it to be 2.19×10^{-4} .

Korschuhov *et al.* (*Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1957, 2, 68) have studied the citrate, tartrate, and oxalate complexes of Cd (II) and Zn (II) by the ion exchange method, using the radioactive isotopes. The average values of the instability constants of the compounds, [Cd(C₂O₄)₂]²⁻; [Cd(C₆H₄O₆)₂]²⁻; [Zn(C₂O₄)₂]²⁻; [Zn(C₆H₄O₆)₂]²⁻ and [Zn(C₆H₅O₇)²⁻] are 2.26×10^{-6} , 3.25×10^{-5} , 7.7×10^{-6} , 2.3×10^{-6} and 2.8×10^{-4} respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three pH titrations and two conductivity titrations, performed for the investigation of zinc citrate complex, are recorded in Tables A, and A₂ respectively.

TABLE A₁
pH titrations.

Expt. No.	Temp.	Soln. titrated.	Contents of the soln. titrated.	Soln. and conc. used.	Results.
I	33°	130 c.c.	H ₃ Cit NaClO ₄	0.0030 g. moles 0.0250	NaOH 0.5 N Fig. 1a, Curve A.
	33°	130	H ₃ Cit ZnSO ₄ NaClO ₄	0.0030 0.0025 0.0250	NaOH 0.5N Fig.-1a, Curve B.
II	33°	100	NaClO ₄	0.0250	Na ₃ Cit 0.1M Fig. 2a, Curve A.
	33°	100	NaClO ₄ ZnSO ₄	0.0250 0.00125	Na ₃ Cit 0.1M Fig-2a, Curve B.
III°	33° ± 0.5°	120	Na ₃ Cit NaClO ₄	0.010 0.025	NaOH 0.1N Fig-3a, Curve A.
	33° ± 0.5°	120	Na ₃ Cit ZnSO ₄ NaClO ₄	0.010 0.001 0.035	NaOH 0.1N Fig. 3a, Curve B.

TABLE A₂*Conductometric titrations.*

Expt. No.	Temp.	Soln. titrated.	Contents of the soln. titrated.	Soln. and conc. used.	Results.	
IV	33°	259 c.c.	H ₃ Cit	0.00030 g.mole	NaOH 0.1N	Fig. 4a, Curve A.
	33°	259	H ₃ Cit ZnSO ₄	0.00030 0.00025	NaOH 0.1N	
V	32.5° ± 0.5°	270	Conductivity water		Na ₃ Cit 0.1M	Fig. 5a, Curve A
	32.5° ± 0.5°	270	ZnSO ₄	0.00010	Na ₃ Cit 0.1M	Fig. 5a, Curve B

For the investigations of manganese citrate complex, four pH titrations and two conductivity titrations were performed. The results are recorded in Tables B₁ and B₂ respectively.

TABLE B₁*pH titrations.*

Expt. No.	Temp.	Soln. titrated.	Contents of the soln. titrated.	Soln. and conc. used.	Results.	
I	33°	105 c.c.	H ₃ Cit NaClO ₄	0.003 g.mole 0.025	NaOH 0.2N	Fig 1 b, Curve A.
	33°	105	H ₃ Cit NaClO ₄ MnSO ₄	0.003 0.025 0.0025	NaOH 0.2N	Fig. 1 b, Curve B
II	33°	85	H ₃ Cit NaClO ₄	0.005 0.025	NaOH 0.95N	Fig. 2b, Curve A.
	33°	85	H ₃ Cit NaClO ₄ MnSO ₄	0.005 0.025 0.0005	NaOH 0.95N	Fig. 2b, Curve B
III.	33° ± 0.5°	100	NaClO ₄	0.025	Na ₃ Cit 0.1M	Fig. 3b, Curve A.
	33° ± 0.5°	100	MnSO ₄ NaClO ₄	0.00125 0.025	Na ₃ Cit 0.1M	Fig. 3b, Curve B.
IV	33°	60	NaClO ₄ Na ₃ Cit	0.010 0.005	NaOH 0.1N	Fig. 4 b, Curve A.
	33°	60	Na ₃ Cit NaClO ₄ MnSO ₄	0.005 0.010 0.0005	NaOH 0.1N	Fig. 4b, Curve B.

TABLE B₂*Conductometric titrations.*

Expt. No.	Temp.	Soln. titrated.	Contents of the soln. titrated.	Soln. and conc. used.	Results.
V	33°	208 c.c.	H ₃ Cit	0.00033 g.mole NaOH 0.1N	Fig. 5b, Curve A.
	33°	208	H ₃ Cit MnSO ₄	0.00033 0.00025 NaOH 0.1N	Fig. 5b, Curve B.
VI	32°	110	Conductivity water	Na ₃ Cit 0.1M	Fig. 6b, Curve A.
	32°	110	MnSO ₄	0.0005 Na ₃ Cit 0.1M	Fig. 6b, Curve B.

DISCUSSION

As found in the study of nickel citrate and other systems, discussed before, the *pH* of the system (B) in each case is lower than the corresponding *pH* in the system (A). Acid is therefore liberated due to the complex formation between the metal ion and citric acid in experiment (I). In case of Zn, the horizontal distance between the two curves at first increases and then decreases. The two curves, however, do not converge and come very close to each other near about the neutralisation point. The two curves are found to diverge above *pH* 7, indicating further liberation of acid in the higher *pH* range.

FIG. 1a

FIG. 1b

In case of manganese also the horizontal distance increases to pH 5.2 and then decreases to pH 6.6. At pH 6.6 the horizontal distance between the two curves is very small, but the two curves diverge in the higher pH region, indicating liberation of a proton probably from co-ordinated water molecule or hydroxyl group. No proton, however, appears to have been liberated below pH 6.6 from the hydroxyl group of citrate ligand due to complex formation, since citric acid would have behaved as a tetrabasic acid in such a case. In

FIG. 2a

experiment II (manganese) the amount of acid liberated is very nearly the same as that obtained in experiment I (Mn). This indicates the formation of a complex containing one citrate ligand per atom of manganese. Formation of a complex containing more than one ligand per atom of manganese even in the system containing metal to citrate in the ratio 1:10 is not indicated.

0.95 N-NaOH added (c.c.).

FIG 2b

Calculation of the Equilibrium Constant

The reaction taking place in expt. (I) in the lower pH range is assumed to be similar to that in the cadmium citrate system (Pattnaik and Pani, this *Journal*, 1957, 24, 673) and may be represented by equation (1) and the equilibrium constant by equation (1-1).

(where M = Mn or Zn)

$$\frac{[C] [H^+]^n}{[M^{2+}] \times [H_3Cit]} = K \quad \dots \quad (1-1)$$

By proceeding in the manner as described in the cadmium citrate system (Pattnaik and Pani, *loc. cit.*) it can be shown that

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] \frac{a}{b} \cdot \Delta[Ct]}{[C]} = n - \frac{a}{b}$$

and when the formation of the complex is complete

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] \frac{a}{b} \cdot \Delta[Ct]}{[MSO_4]} = n - \frac{a}{b}$$

$\Delta[NaOH]$, $\Delta[Ct]$, $[ZnSO_4]$, $[MnSO_4]$, a , and b were calculated as before.

Substituting these values, a series of values of n are calculated for zinc and manganese complexes and collected in Table IA and Table IB. In case of zinc, the value of n is less than 2 below pH 3.4 and increases to about 2.8 at pH 5.2.

TABLE IA

pH.	$\Delta [\text{NaOH}] \times 10^2$.	$\Delta [\text{Cl}] \times 10^4$.	a/b .	$[\text{ZnSO}_4] \times 10^2$.	n .	$[\text{C}] \times 10^3$.	$[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}] \times 10^2$.	$[\text{Zn}^{2+}] \times 10^2$.	$K \times 10^5$.
2.5	0.2625	1.1	0.2131	1.893	0.3529	1.482	1.6780	1.745	5.059
2.6	0.372	1.5	0.2560	1.892	0.4557	2.156	1.5300	1.827	5.335
2.7	0.515	2.4	0.3046	1.889	0.5839	3.079	1.3580	1.561	5.780
2.8	0.582	2.7	0.3589	1.859	0.6768	3.361	1.2310	1.523	4.502
2.9	0.720	3.3	0.4184	1.848	0.8157	4.611	1.0420	1.384	5.098
3.0	0.856	3.9	0.4822	1.835	0.9584	5.761	0.8720	1.259	5.216
3.1	1.024	4.7	0.5499	1.824	1.1252	7.235	0.6981	1.101	5.939
3.2	1.119	5.2	0.6197	1.812	1.2548	8.341	0.5591	0.978	6.089
3.3	1.283	6.0	0.6911	1.801	1.4263	10.12	0.4111	0.789	7.834
3.7	1.802	8.5	0.9797	1.768	2.0520				
3.8	1.822	8.5	1.052	1.750	2.1560				
3.9	1.842	8.5	1.127	1.744	2.2380				
4.0	1.861	8.6	1.204	1.736	2.3320				
4.1	1.849	8.5	1.282	1.732	2.3890				
4.2	1.804	8.2	1.362	1.726	2.4710				
4.3	1.783	8.2	1.445	1.722	2.5370				
4.4	1.778	8.0	1.530	1.717	2.6550				
4.5	1.709	7.9	1.615	1.712	2.6890				
4.8	1.467	6.8	1.876	1.703	2.8110				
5.0	1.237	5.7	2.049	1.700	2.8446				
5.2	0.984	4.5	2.213	1.699	2.7980				

TABLE IB

pH.	$\Delta [\text{NaOH}] \times 10^3$.	$\Delta [\text{Cl}] \times 10^4$.	$[\text{MnSO}_4]$.	a/b .	n .	$[\text{C}] \times 10^3$.	$[\text{Mn}^{2+}] \times 10^2$.	$[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}] \times 10^2$.	$K \times 10^5$.
2.5	1.853	2.7	0.02281	0.2131	0.2968	1.069	2.174	2.078	2.367
2.6	2.07	2.9	0.02252	0.2560	0.3512	1.229	2.129	1.932	1.887
2.7	2.15	4.0	0.02219	0.3046	0.4070	1.340	2.085	1.774	1.442
2.8	2.79	4.1	0.02193	0.3588	0.4928	1.789	2.014	1.954	1.401
2.9	2.89	4.1	0.02166	0.4184	0.5598	1.935	1.973	1.431	1.086
3.0	2.74	4.1	0.02144	0.4822	0.6192	1.935	1.950	1.275	0.7785
3.1	3.68	6.3	0.02114	0.5499	0.7381	2.739	1.840	1.078	0.8712
3.2	4.49	6.4	0.02083	0.6197	0.8542	3.536	1.729	0.8932	0.9120
3.3	4.98	7.1	0.02059	0.6911	0.9568	4.184	1.641	0.7345	0.8714
3.4	5.59	8.0	0.02032	0.7632	1.0684	5.013	1.531	0.5866	0.8944
3.5	6.32	9.1	0.02006	0.8351	1.1860	6.077	1.399	0.4531	0.9583
3.6	6.86	9.8	0.01981	0.9078	1.2990	7.098	1.272	0.3437	1.0249
3.7	7.92	11.3	0.01952	0.9797	1.4423	8.841	1.068	0.2416	1.3640
3.8	8.65	12.3	0.01923	1.052	1.5691	10.490	0.874	0.1851	1.8260
3.9	9.20	13.1	0.01897	1.127	1.6894	12.220	0.675	0.1075	2.6680
4.0	9.49	13.5	0.01871	1.204	1.7977	13.960	0.475	0.0664	4.4300
4.3	10.70	15.4	0.01803	1.445	2.1619				
4.4	10.70	16.0	0.01785	1.530	2.2658				
4.5	10.86	15.6	0.01770	1.615	2.3808				
4.8	9.92	14.2	0.01734	1.876	2.6016				
5.0	9.43	13.6	0.01712	2.049	2.7629				
5.2	7.98	11.4	0.01698	2.213	2.8313				

N/10-NaOH added (c.c.)
FIG. 3a.

0.1M-Na citrate added (c.c.)
FIG. 3b

In the case of manganese, the value of n is less than 2 below pH 4.1 and increases with increasing pH but less than 3 below pH 5.2.

TABLE II A

pH.	$[C_1^-]/[ZnSO_4]$.	$[C]/[ZnSO_4]$.	$K_1 \times 10^5$.
3.7	0.052	0.948	1.096
3.8	0.156	0.844	2.929
3.9	0.238	0.762	3.931
4.0	0.332	0.668	4.969
4.1	0.389	0.611	5.058
4.2	0.471	0.529	5.616
4.3	0.537	0.463	5.813
4.4	0.655	0.345	7.558
4.5	0.689	0.311	7.004
4.8	0.811	0.189	6.800
5.0	0.8446	0.155	5.449
5.2	0.796	0.202	2.492

TABLE II B

pH.	$n-2$.	$3-n$	$K_1 \times 10^5$
4.3	0.1619	0.8381	0.968
4.4	0.2658	0.7342	1.441
4.5	0.3808	0.6192	1.942
4.8	0.6016	0.3984	2.399
5.0	0.7629	0.2371	3.218
5.2	0.8313	0.1687	3.110

At lower pH the complex is formed with the liberation of two protons due to the reaction of Zn^{2+} or Mn^{2+} and citric acid. Hence the complex is a neutral one. This subsequently ionises like an acid. The reaction may be represented by equation (2) and the equilibrium constant by equation (2-1).

$$\frac{[C_1^-][H^+]}{[C]} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad (2-1)$$

It can be shown as before that

$$\frac{(n-2)[H^+]}{(3-n)} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad (2-2)$$

[C], [H₃Cit], [Zn²⁺] and [Mn²⁺], are calculated as before. The values of equilibrium constant K , obtained by using these values, are shown in Tables IA and IB respectively for zinc and manganese. The mean values of K are 6.36×10^{-5} and 1.33×10^{-5} for Zn and Mn respectively. The values of C and C₁⁻ and the equilibrium constant K , are calculated as before by equation (2-2) and tabulated in Table IIA and Table IIB for Zn and Mn respectively. The mean value of K , are 4.89×10^{-5} and 1.93×10^{-5} for Zn and Mn respectively

In expt. II of Zn and expt. III of Mn, the curve B is exactly similar to that obtained with the cobalt citrate system in an exactly similar experiment. The pH of the system containing no metal ion (Curve A) rapidly rises at the beginning and then rises very slowly with the increasing concentration of sodium citrate. In the system containing metal ion (Zn or Mn) (Curve B) the pH falls rapidly at the beginning and then remains very nearly constant for some time. The pH increases afterwards rapidly with increasing amount of sodium citrate till the point P is reached. After the point, the rise in pH is comparatively slow.

The reaction of Zn²⁺ or Mn²⁺ ion with citrate ligands results in the formation of a complex and liberation of a proton. The reaction would therefore be similar to that represented in the cobalt citrate system. (Pattnaik and Pani, this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 364). Hence

(where M = Zn or Mn)

$$\frac{[C_2^{2-}][H^+]}{[M^{2+}][\text{Cit}^{3-}]} = K, \quad \dots \quad (3-1)$$

The reaction alone cannot explain the results since the *pH* does not fall continuously till the formation of the complex is complete. Another reaction is expected to exist which would remove at least some of the protons liberated by the above reaction. Since very little free citrate ions would exist in the solution, removal of protons by citrate ions to any appreciable extent is not expected. The protons are therefore removed by the complex C_2^{2-} by reaction (4).

$$\frac{[C_2^{2-}][H^+]}{[C_1^-]} = K_2 \quad \dots \quad (4-1)$$

The complex C_2^{2-} would exist only in the higher *pH* range and when the *pH* is lowered, it is converted to C_1^- by the above reaction.

0.1 N-NaOH added (c.c.)
FIG. 5b

0.1 M-Na citrate added (c.c.)
FIG. 6b

At the beginning, more of C_2^{2-} is formed and hence the *pH* falls rapidly. When the *pH* is sufficiently lowered, the complex C_2^{2-} is no longer formed, but the complex C_1^- is formed by reaction (4) or (5). This would produce the same result.

The concentration of C_2^{2-} does not increase and there is no liberation of acid due to formation of C_1^- ; as such the *pH* remains very nearly constant for some time. After this the *pH* rises comparatively rapidly due to increasing concentration of free citrate ion in the solution. As the *pH* is increased, reaction (4) moves in the reverse direction. There is a break in curve B at point P. This comes when a little more than one g. mole of sodium citrate per g. atom of metal concerned is added. This break most probably in-

diates complete formation of the 1:1 zinc citrate and manganese citrate complexes. Above the inflection point, the reaction taking place is the dissociation of the complex C_1^- to H^+ and C_2^{2-} .

K_4 was determined as before above the inflection point as calculated in the cobalt citrate system (Pattnaik and Pani, *loc. cit.*). The values are shown in Table IIIA and IIIB. The mean values of K_2 are 2.000×10^{-8} and 3.07×10^{-9} for Zn and Mn respectively.

TABLE IIIA

pH.	[ZnSO ₄].	[Ct].	Z.	[HCit ²⁻]×10 ⁴ .	[C ₂ ²⁻]×10 ⁴ .	[C ₁ ⁻].	$K_2 \times 10^8$.
6.25	0.01086	0.01304	6.7750	3.218	3.303	0.01053	1.765
6.30	0.01077	0.01379	7.4773	4.041	4.138	0.01036	2.002
6.35	0.01069	0.01453	8.2829	4.648	4.749	0.01022	2.076
6.40	0.01055	0.01553	9.1487	5.445	5.547	0.01000	2.209
6.45	0.01039	0.01694	10.1307	6.460	6.569	0.00974	2.393
6.50	0.01023	0.01817	11.2477	7.063	7.167	0.00952	2.381
6.55	0.01008	0.01936	12.4969	7.429	7.532	0.00933	2.275
6.60	0.00990	0.02070	13.9061	7.821	7.905	0.00911	2.179
6.65	0.00972	0.02224	15.4755	8.093	8.183	0.00890	2.058
6.70	0.00950	0.02402	17.2449	8.424	8.498	0.00865	1.960
6.80	0.00902	0.02785	21.4439	8.784	8.850	0.00813	1.725

TABLE IIIB

pH.	[Ct].	[MnSO ₄].	Y.	[HCit ²⁻]×10 ⁴ .	[C ₂ ²⁻]×10 ⁴ .	[C ₁ ⁻].	$K_2 \times 10^9$.
6.75	0.01335	0.01137	19.2243	1.930	1.042	0.01126	1.646
6.80	0.01481	0.01118	21.4438	1.693	1.708	0.01101	2.458
6.85	0.01639	0.01097	23.9434	2.264	2.810	0.01074	3.000
6.90	0.01803	0.01076	26.7331	2.719	2.737	0.01049	3.285
6.95	0.01948	0.01057	29.8727	2.984	2.999	0.01027	3.275
7.00	0.02138	0.01031	33.4024	3.313	3.331	0.00998	3.337

Below the inflection point Zn and Mn exist partly as Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} and partly as complexes. Hence

$$[MSO_4] = [M^{2+}] + [C_1^-] + [C_2^{2-}].$$

K_4 was calculated as before (as determined in cobalt citrate system). The values are collected in Tables IVA and IVB.

TABLE IVA

pH.	[Ct]×10 ³ .	[ZnSO ₄] ×10 ² .	r.	p.	q.	[HCit ²⁻] ×10 ⁵ .	[C ₂ ²⁻] ×10 ⁵ .	[C ₁ ⁻] ×10 ³ .	[Zn ²⁺] ×10 ² .	[Cit ³⁻] ×10 ⁴ .	$K_4 \times 10^5$.
5.89	5.361	1.180	1.0633	3.5466	62.20	8.011	8.643	5.290	0.643	2.05	8.447
5.90	4.762	1.191	1.0618	3.6039	60.81	6.889	7.444	4.450	0.739	1.70	7.461
5.95	3.474	1.206	1.0551	3.9145	54.31	5.578	5.996	3.196	0.881	1.64	7.650
6.00	2.534	1.218	1.0514	4.2645	48.51	4.504	4.825	2.292	0.984	1.49	3.291
6.05	2.056	1.224	1.0438	4.6579	43.35	4.039	4.306	1.824	1.038	1.49	2.481
6.10	1.671	1.229	1.0390	5.0985	38.74	3.619	3.839	1.449	1.081	1.48	1.905
6.15	1.390	1.233	1.0348	5.5934	34.63	3.273	3.457	1.162	1.114	1.52	1.445
6.20	1.186	1.235	1.0310	6.1505	30.97	3.064	3.222	0.966	1.136	1.58	1.132
6.25	0.990	1.238	1.0276	6.7748	27.72	2.768	2.899	0.775	1.158	1.60	0.882
6.30	0.5965	1.243	1.0246	7.4773	24.81	1.777	1.870	0.445	1.197	1.16	0.576

The mean value of K_4 are 3.85×10^{-5} and 2.99×10^{-6} for Zn and Mn respectively.

TABLE IVB

pH.	[C] $\times 10^3$.	[MnSO ₄]	P.	q.	r.	[HCit ²⁻] $\times 10^5$.	[Ca ²⁺] $\times 10^3$.	[C ₁ ⁻] $\times 10^3$.	[Mn ²⁺] $\times 10^3$.	[Cit ³⁻] $\times 10^4$.	$K_4 \times 10^6$.
6.70	3.661	0.01265	17.2449	65.98	1.0098	4.350	4.413	2.887	9.74	7.07	1.278
6.65	5.124	0.01246	15.4755	73.91	1.0110	5.663	5.749	4.192	8.21	8.19	1.914
6.62	6.542	0.01227	14.5159	79.12	1.0117	6.896	7.003	5.471	6.73	9.33	2.675
6.65	9.419	0.01189	15.4755	73.91	1.0110	10.420	10.560	7.698	4.08	15.12	3.831
6.70	11.340	0.01163	17.2449	65.98	1.0098	13.510	13.670	8.882	2.61	21.90	4.772

Now it can be shown that

$$\frac{K_4 \times k_1 k_2 k_3}{K_1 \times K_2} = \frac{[C] [H^+]^2}{[M^{2+}] [H_3Cit]} = K$$

By substituting the values of K , K_1 , K_2 , K_4 , k_1 , k_2 , and k_3 , it is found that the values of

$$\frac{K_4 \times k_1 k_2 k_3}{K_1 \times K_2}$$

are equal to 0.366×10^{-3} and 0.5348×10^{-5} for Zn and Mn respectively, whereas the value of K (obtained before in the expt. I) is 5.73×10^{-3} for zinc and 1.331×10^{-3} for manganese. Hence both the values are not equal as seen in the case of cobalt, discussed before. The low value of

$$\frac{K_4 \times k_1 k_2 k_3}{K_1 \times K_2}$$

may be due to the low value of K_4 , which might have been due to the hydrolysis of Zn^{2+} ion to $ZnOH^+$ ion and Mn^{2+} to $MnOH^+$ according to equation (6). This type of hydrolysis may occur to an appreciable extent at higher pH. The K_4 is determined above pH 5.9 in case of Zn and above 6.6 in case of Mn, but K is determined at pH below 3.4 in both cases.

The hydrolysis constant of this reaction may be represented by equation (6-1).

$$K_h = \frac{[MOH^+] [H^+]}{[M^{2+}]} \quad \dots \quad (6-1)$$

Calculation of Hydrolysis Constant

Since Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} ions are partly hydrolysed, the free zinc and free manganese assumed to be present as Zn^{2+} or Mn^{2+} , calculated for the determination of K_4 , are not correct. Therefore the concentration of Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} would be less. The value of K_4 would therefore be more. It is assumed that the hydrolysis of Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} below pH 3.4 is negligible.

The hydrolysis constant was calculated in a manner similar to that adopted for the calculation of the hydrolysis constant of the cobalt ion (*loc. cit.*). The values are given in Tables VA and VB for Zn and Mn respectively. The mean values of K_h are 1.35×10^{-3} for Zn and 2.97×10^{-7} for Mn.

Further, it is mentioned in the International Critical Table (Vol. 7, p. 252) that hydrolysis of Zn^{2+} to $ZnOH^+$ according to equation (6) is 0.0416% and 0.0244% in aqueous solutions of zinc sulphate of concentration 0.0157M and 0.0244 M respectively.

The hydrolysis constant K_h , if calculated from the above results, would be 2.83×10^{-5} and 3.97×10^{-5} respectively. Hence the results obtained in this experiment agree with the above results of Zn.

TABLE VA

pH.	$[Zn] \times 10^2$.	$\frac{K_4 k_1 k_2 k_3}{K \times K_1 \times K_2}$	$[Zn^{2+}] \times 10^4$.	$[ZnOH^+]$.	$K_h \times 10^5$.
5.90	0.739	0.06303	4.724	0.00692	1.844
6.00	0.984	"	6.291	0.00923	1.485
6.10	1.091	"	6.910	0.01012	1.163
6.2)	1.136	"	7.233	0.01064	0.924

TABLE VB

pH.	$[Mn] \times 10^3$.	$\frac{K_4 k_1 k_2 k_3}{K \times K_1 \times K_2}$	$[Mn^{2+}] \times 10^3$.	$[MnOH^+] \times 10^3$.	$K_h \times 10^7$.
6.75	11.38	0.4026	4.582	6.80	2.638
6.70	9.74	"	3.922	5.83	2.961
6.65	8.21	"	3.306	4.90	3.319

In expt. III for Zn and expt. IV for Mn the results are very nearly identical to that obtained in similar experiment in the cobalt citrate system. The curve B is similar to the neutralisation curve of an acid. It is of interest to note that the neutralisation point is reached at about 11 c.c. of 0.1N-NaOH in case of Zn and at 5.5. c.c. of the same alkali in case of manganese.

The pH attained by the solution containing Zn by the addition of 11 c.c. of 0.1N alkali is reached by the other solution on addition of 1 c.c. of the same alkali, i.e., 0.001g. mole of sodium hydroxide is consumed by the complex formed from 0.001 g. mole of zinc sulphate. The pH attained by the solution containing Mn by the addition of 5.5. c.c. of N/10 alkali is reached by the other solution on adding 0.5 c.c. of the same alkali, i.e., 0.0005 g. moles of NaOH is consumed by the complex formed from 0.0005 g. moles of manganese sulphate. Further liberation of one equivalent of proton indicates the formation of C_2 complex in each case.

In expt. IV of zinc and expt. V of manganese, the nature of the curves A and B are similar to those obtained in the case of cobalt citrate system. A break in curve B, similar to that in curve A at the neutralisation point, comes much later, indicating the former system to contain more acid.

A neutral complex is formed in the beginning which does not contribute to the conductance of the solution. The neutral complex then dissociates like dibasic acid to complexes C_1^- and C_2^{2-} . The formation of these complexes are indicated by breaks at P_1 , P_2 , and P_3 respectively.

In expt. V of Zn and expt. VI of Mn, the nature of the curves is similar to that obtained in the investigation of the cobalt citrate system. Hence the formation of 1:1 complex is indicated here also

The structure of the zinc citrate and manganese citrate complexes are just similar to that of cadmium citrate complexes (Pattnaik and Pani, *loc. cit.*, p. 673) and nickel citrate complexes (Pattnaik and Pani, this *Journal* 1957, **34**, 619) discussed earlier.

The authors are thankful to the B. S. I. R. (Government of Orissa) for the financial assistance given to them during this investigation.

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Received October 31, 1960.